

**MATERIAL AND TECHNICAL CONDITION OF LIGHT
INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN FERGANA REGIO**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7907984>

Abstract: In the article. After the Second World War, there was talk about the material and technical condition of light industrial enterprises in Fergana region. The territory of Uzbekistan has long been specialized in the production of thread and silk fabrics, such fabrics as satin, bekasam, banoras are popular in many countries of the world. Therefore, even in the years under review, light industrial enterprises had a special place in the economic region of Uzbekistan.

Key words: light industry, spinning factory, light industry, Lubli fiber, collective export, knitted products

Even before the Second World War, a lot of attention was paid to the development of light industry in Uzbekistan, and the Fergana spinning factory, which was launched in the 1930s, was one of the first factories in the republic. Knitted products were produced in the Kokan hosiery-knitting factory, which was launched in 1939, as well as in Andijan, Tashkent knitting factories, Samarkand, Bukhara, Jizzakh upper knitting factories. As for shoe production, it was launched in Tashkent, Samarkand, Kokand, Bukhara, Yangiyol, Chirchik, Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, and Pop factories[1]. In general, by 1940, there were 15 processing of agricultural raw materials in the light industry of Uzbekistan - cotton ginning, carding, wool washing, netting and production of consumer goods - yarn spinning, silk weaving. , knitwear, shoes and other industries were available.

After the end of the Second World War, in the process of restoring the economy of the Soviet state and moving it to a peaceful path, the light industry of Uzbekistan was also mobilized to fulfill the seven-year plans. The five-year plans focused on the restoration of the national economy. The composition of Uzbekistan's light industry sector is also different, and it was as follows.

**Network structure of the textile industry of Uzbekistan
(1960-1970s) [2]**

No	tworks	1960 y	1970 y
1	Textile industry	100	100
2	Cotton cleaning	66,7	72,9
3	First processing of lube fibers	1,1	1,7
4	The first treatment of wool	0,7	0,6
5	Silk fabric	2,1	1,5
6	Yarn industry	16,0	9,2
7	Sherst	0,2	0,1
9	Textile haberdashery	0,7	1,4
10	Knitting	1,8	3,9

From the table above, it can be seen that Uzbekistan is a republic that produces the main raw materials, where special attention is paid to the development of light industry, but production in this area is far behind. According to I. Iskanderov, such slow development was due to the inability to fully use domestic resources. The author emphasizes that this industry is far behind other industries in the republic. Nevertheless, during the eighth five-year period (1966-1970), which is considered the most developed period of the economy in the history of the Soviet country, efforts to develop light industry in the republic were intensified.

According to statistical data, the growth of the entire industry was 6.3 percent in 1966-1970, while the textile industry grew by 2.2 percent[3]. In addition, the Institute of Economics and the "Central Asia and Kazakhstan" sector of the State Planning Committee of the USSR developed a large project called "Location and development of industrial enterprises in the USSR in 1966-1970 and 1971-1980" in this five-year period. "Uzbekistan's productive forces and their development and prospects" regarding the placement of light industrial enterprises in Central Asia, in particular in Uzbekistan, "The scheme for the placement and development of production forces in Uzbekistan in 1975-1980", "Middle The projects within the framework of the topics "Issues of placement and development of production forces in the perspectives of the republics of Asia and Kazakhstan" took place[4]. This, of course, was one of the steps taken to develop light industry in the republic, which grows raw cotton.

Due to the great need for silk and thread fabrics, gray, gauze, white chit, etc. in terms of climate and nationality, the contribution of production of these fabrics is high, on average it was 70 percent. . Although there are many projects and allocated funds for the development of light industry, the products produced in the republic are not enough to satisfy the needs of the local population. Due to the limited assortment, yarn fabrics are brought to Uzbekistan from 10 allied republics and 8 foreign countries. 96.6 percent of the fabrics imported from the allied republics were imported, 75.6 percent of which fell to the central regions of the RSFSR, Moscow and Ivanovo regions. In this regard, the republics of Central Asia and Kazakhstan are in the second place, it was 16.2 percent. Among the countries where fabrics are imported from abroad, India ranks first, and Hungary ranks second.

During this period, a number of measures were taken to improve the republic's industry, but Uzbekistan was among the least industrially developed republics among the allied republics. In particular, even by 1981, 45-46 percent of fabrics were brought to Uzbekistan from textile enterprises in the RSFSR. Also, 10.8% of fabrics, 20.5% of knitwear, 10% of sewing products were imported from Belarus, 70% of textile products from the republics of the Caucasus, 32% of knitted products from Lithuania and Latvia. At the moment, the republic, which could not satisfy its needs with light industrial products, exported products to 23 countries of the world, and it was more Asian and African countries.[6]

During this period, enterprises belonging to the light industry of Uzbekistan took appropriate measures to increase the variety and quality of their products in order to increase the volume of collective exports. In particular, in 1966-1970, enterprises under the Ministry of Light Industry of Uzbekistan introduced more than 5,000 new models and mastered the production of more than 80 new products.

In 1970, 45 types of gauze, 40 types of hosiery, sewing products and hundreds of new types of shoes, which were new in terms of structure and weaving, were put into production. By January 1, 1972, 450 enterprises were operating in the light industry of the republic, including 62 enterprises belonging to the Ministry of Light Industry and 102 enterprises

belonging to the Ministry of Cotton Cleaning Industry[7]. Some of the fabrics woven in light industrial enterprises were exported to other Central Asian republics. Uzbekistan has a place not only in the economic regions of Greater Central Asia, but also in the whole country. In 1983, the production of light industry in the republic's industry made up 38.6% of industrial products.

During this period, Uzbekistan sent to the RSFSR 22% of the yarn-making products produced in the republic, 31% of silk fabrics, 14% of sewing products and some knitted products. The exchange of goods was carried out in a higher volume with Ukraine, where 20% of silk and 10% of yarn fabrics were exported. About 28 percent of light industrial products, 21 percent of silk fabrics, and 40 percent of sewing products were also sent to Kazakhstan[8]. In 1981, 30 percent of yarn fabrics, 16.3 percent of silk fabrics, and 45.3 percent of sewing products were exported from the Uzbek SSR to the Kyrgyz SSR, Turkmenistan SSR, and Tajikistan SSR[9].

But not all enterprises were able to fulfill the task of producing high-quality products. In 1970, 346 complaints were filed against the republic's garment factories, and they were fined 80,000 rubles for producing low-quality products. In fact, due to the low quality of stitching and decorations of the products produced in the knitting factory, no buyers were found. In the case of the regional footwear factory, the quality of the produced products could not meet the standard due to the violation of the technological regime of production, the lack of control over raw materials and semi-finished products, as well as the failure to make timely demands on the supplier. As a result, the variety of products produced by the factory was reduced[10]. At the moment, light industrial enterprises provided 40% of the revenue from turnover, while the state budget of the republic accounted for 15% of the total profit. This situation naturally led to the reduction of the price of the produced product, causing damage to the state [11].

In some cases, the agreement between the allied republics was not followed in the exchange of goods. For example, on November 1, 1970, the first flower-printing factory in Moscow sent to the Andijan base of Uztekstiltorg 26,600 soums of 72,110 articles of undemanding flower staple gas.

Although many enterprises exceeded their production plans, they failed to fulfill the task in terms of product types. In 1970, the garment industry of Uzbekistan increased its production program, but 4.4 million items of 27 items were ordered. could not deliver goods worth soums to trade organizations. This year, the knitting enterprises of the republic sold 10 mln. gave less ruble product [12].

As for the Fergana economic region, in the 1950s, light industry was considered the main branch of the region. This industry accounted for more than 60 percent of the total output, and its composition can be seen in the table below[13].

Light industrial products produced in Ferghana (1950)

Nº	Networks	Number of workers	Gross product
1	Cotton ginning industry	15,7	71,9
2	Yarn industry	18,6	5,1
3	Cocoon processing industry	40,9	13,7
4	Knitting industry	6,8	1,2

5	Sewing industry	14,8	7,2
6	Footwear industry	2,5	0,8
7	Other networks	0,7	0,1
8	Full	100,0	100,0

It should be noted here that the products produced in Fergana were sent to many enterprises of the republic and the union.

In the analyzed years, special attention was paid to the production of synthetic and artificial fibers in the textile industry of Uzbekistan. The production of non-woven textile materials was started in the Fergana economic region, the activity of this industry in the country started in 1959, and in Uzbekistan it started in 1960. Non-woven materials were produced at the "Pyatiletka" factory in Namangan, and this product was much cheaper than other light industrial products.

In Namangan, in 1966-1970, a suit and staple garment factory was launched, and it operated as the only one in the Greater Central Asian Economic Region. Already in those years, the plant was equipped with modern machines for the time. In particular, SVR-1 and VVR with stretching device, PL-66-6 brand spinner, PKL-100 brand spinner-cooker, RL-192 brand spinner with high productivity LNS-51-1 carding, GM-450-7 brand carding and new type of carding machines were installed in the combined spinning factory. In the 1970s, for the first time in the Soviet Union, the production of lavsan and nitron, made of artificial fiber for suits, was launched[14]. A gin factory was built in Namangan in order to supply cotton ginning industry in the republic. This factory produced low-quality cotton fabric. The main enterprise of the Fergana knitting industry is considered to be the largest hosiery weaving plant in the republic. 20 mln. in one year. delivered a pair of socks.

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